

THE CHALLENGE TO PROMOTE IMTA IN A COUNTRY WITH LOW MONOCULTURE PRODUCTION. THE ARGENTINE CASE

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Introduction

Aquaculture is an essential activity contributing to food security, providing 88 million tonnes of aquatic food in 2020 (FAO 2022). Aquaculture continues growing rapidly, with an average annual growth rate of 6.7% between 1990-2020. Nevertheless, 92% of the global production is concentrated in only 20 countries, while 95 out of 170 countries with aquaculture activity produce less than 10,000 tons per year, as is the case of Argentina (Cai et al. 2022). 90% of aquaculture production in Argentina focuses on only two freshwater fish species (*Oncorhynchus mykiss* and *Piaractus mesopotamicus*), while marine aquaculture has been historically a marginal activity.

In this context, the aim of this work was to gather existing and generate new information relevant to promote and develop marine IMTA in Argentina and analyse the potential of low trophic native species to diversify the current production concentrated in fed aquaculture.

Material and Methods

We evaluated the potential of 12 native species of the Beagle Channel, located in the extreme south of Argentina (54°S), for IMTA production. The species were 2 fish, 2 crabs, 1 octopus, 2 sea urchins, 2 bivalves, 2 algae and 1 halophyte, covering the different roles in a theoretical IMTA: Fed aquaculture Organic Extractive Aquaculture (sedimented POM feeders), Organic Extractive Aquaculture (suspended POM feeders), and Organic Extractive Aquaculture (DIN feeders). Besides, several activities were carried out to design strategies to develop IMTA, including assessment of environmental conditions, regulations, markets, and social perception, among others.

Results and Discussion

We detected two groups with potential to be part of an IMTA system: 1) Red sea urchin (*Loxechinus albus*) reared in lantern integrated with blue mussel (*Mytilus chilensis*) reared in longlines. The other proposed system consists in whitebait (*Galaxias maculatus*) integrated with halophytes (*Salicornia magellanica*) in an open land-based system.

The market study showed that blue mussel is one of the most important species, while *Salicornia* (included in the algae category) is little offered. From the interviews with the restaurant managers, it was detected that there is interest in incorporating sea urchins, and they are still unaware of the gastronomic value of whitebait (Figure 2).

One of the strengths detected is that potential producers, decision-makers, and society, have an idea about the meaning of the IMTA concept.

Regarding the limitations found, it is worth mentioning the lack of aquaculture facilities to develop projects on a pilot scale, and a great distrust on the part of society towards aquaculture projects due to their potential environmental impacts and the lack of government capacity to monitor this activity.

Figure 1: Some of the activities carried out in Argentina to boost IMTA development. **1)** Species selection in terms of biological potential, monoculture experiences and technical knowledge. **2)** Design of potential productive cycles of native species. **3)** GIS development gathering information about environmental data, infrastructure available, other uses, etc. **4)** Record of environmental data in areas of interest. **5)** Analysis of atmospheric data (e.g., wind speed and direction). **6)** Participatory workshops with stakeholders to understand needs, opportunities, and weaknesses. **7)** Market study and analysis of the gastronomic value of native species.

Figure 2: Species offered by local seafood restaurant and their importance in terms of offer frequency.

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References

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